

Empirical Research on the Issues of Termination of Employee Relationships Post Pandemi Covid-19. Urgency of the Role of Work Motivation and Employee Trust: Evidence from Indonesia

Mohammad Redy

Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Madura, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Work Motivation and Employee Trust on Termination Anxiety Issues post the COVID-19 Pandemic. This research is classified as Explanatory Research with a quantitative approach. The sample used was 90 employees of PT.Marinal Indo Prima with purposive sampling technique. The type of data used is primary data, namely data collection using a questionnaire. Analysis of the data used is Multiple Linear Regression with SPSS. The results of this study indicate that work motivation has a negative effect on Termination Anxiety Issues. Likewise, Employee Trust has a negative effect on Termination Anxiety Issues. Simultaneously Work Motivation and Employee Trust have an effect on Termination Anxiety Issues.

KEYWORDS: Work Motivation, Employee Trust, Termination Anxiety Issues.

I. INTRODUCTION

The level of disruption during the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the community's economy. One that is quite impactful is the number of layoffs. Anxiety is a feeling of worry, fear that is not clear why, but anxiety is also a great force in driving behavior, both deviant and disturbed. Aisyah (2016), expresses anxiety as an emotion characterized by an anticipated feeling of danger, including the tension and stress that confronts it and by the arousal of sympathetic nerves. Anxiety arises initially from unpleasant stimuli received by the sensory organs. Information from sensory devices continues on the sympathetic nerves, giving rise to a response to a stimulus in the form of changes in a person's psychological to physical condition. Anxiety is a condition of apprehension or worry about a danger or bad thing that will happen soon. Anxiety in facing termination of employment is a condition or feeling that is unpleasant and subjective in nature experienced by individuals who are about to enter a period of retirement. The source of which is not clear causes individuals to feel afraid, uncomfortable thoughts and confused feelings to face the future. According to Kube (2017), suggested that work anxiety can be managed. Therefore it is important to pay attention to other factors so that anxiety does not have a negative impact on the progress of the company or institution. According SchultzA Maformulates the notion of termination of employment as the end of an employment relationship between workers and employers because one party cannot fulfill its obligations or because the work agreement between workers and employers ends. Mass layoffs will cause anxiety as experienced by employees. According to Wahyudi (2022), explained that anxiety is tension, insecurity, and worry that arises because it is felt that something unpleasant will happen. Someone experiences anxiety due to the accumulation of problems faced, causing tension and worry. Anxiety as a manifestation of tension and worry will make individuals feel insecure and uncomfortable in carrying out an activity. According to Widyantari (2020) said that individuals who experience anxiety can be seen from four components, namely psychological, somatic, cognitive and motor.

Having a workforce that effectively performs its job functions is essential for an organization to remain competitive. Employee motivation is very important for the success of the organization. Support for employee work motivation can be realized if the needs of each employee can be fulfilled, so it can be said that the level of employee motivation can be influenced by how far the needs of each employee are fulfilled. Meeting the needs of employees is an important factor for creating incentives for employees to do a good job so that ultimately organizational goals can be achieved. According Irwan, (2020), argues that motivation is the key to a successful organization to maintain the continuity of work within the organization in a strong way and help to survive. Motivation is providing the right guidance or direction, resources and rewards to get them inspired and interested to work the way they want.

According to Fulmer (2012), one of the factors that influence it is the level of self-confidence of a person. Lauster (2003), states that self-confidence is an attitude or belief in one's own abilities, so that in interacting with others, they have an achievement drive and can recognize their own strengths and weaknesses. Someone who has a good level of self-confidence, the level of anxiety facing

Empirical Research on the Issues of Termination of Employee Relationships Post Pandemi Covid-19. Urgency of the Role of Work Motivation and Employee Trust: Evidence from Indonesia

termination of employment tends to be low, because individuals can quickly realize their anxiety so that they can suppress or minimize the impact of anxiety facing termination of employment.

Ma'rifatullah, (2016), in his research stated that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and self-confidence on the issue of termination of employment, whereas according to Gunawan, (2017), there is a not so significant effect between self-belief on the issue of termination of employment, while work motivation has a positive effect.

According to Hasibuan, (2005), motivation is the provision of driving force that raises one's enthusiasm for work, so that one wants to cooperate, work effectively and integrate with all one's efforts to achieve satisfaction. Individuals who have good work motivation and have self-confidence will not feel anxious about various things that will happen in their life. So that termination of employment that will occur at any time will not cause problems for both workers and the company. Individuals will realize the end of the work relationship so that each has tried to prepare itself to face this reality (Duggan, J. 2020). Aisyah, (2016), in her research stated that there was a significant influence between termination of employment policies and work motivation, while research conducted by Widyantari (2020), stated that the results of research on anxiety facing termination of employment had no significant effect on work motivation. Based on the description above, the authors are interested in researching and analyzing whether there is an influence between Work Motivation and Employee Trust on the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment at PT. Marinal Indo Prima. Based on the problems above, this study aims to identify and analyze the role of work motivation and employee trust in the issue of anxiety about termination of employment.

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

The Relationship between Work Motivation and the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment.

Maslow developed a need-based theory of motivation. Maslow identified and analyzed five basic needs that he believed underlies all human behavior, these needs relate to physiology, security, affiliation, self-esteem and self-actualization (Anderman, E. M. 2020). Furthermore, Maduka & Okafor (2014) argue that motivation is a process of arousing behavior, maintaining the progress of behavior and channeling specific behaviors and actions, thus work motivation is the need and desire that encourages employees to act. Lower-level needs such as physiological and safety needs must be met before higher-level needs such as belonging and self-actualization. According to the implications of Maslow's hierarchy of needs, individuals must have lower levels of needs fulfilled, for example safe working conditions, adequate wages to meet the needs of self, family and job security before they will be motivated by increased job responsibilities, status and challenging work tasks. (Tóth-Király, I. Et al. 2020). Employee motivation in the company is very dependent on the conditions of the company where employees work. Companies that are experiencing unbearable losses such as: decreased profits, high increases in operational costs, and the company's inability to meet employee salary payments will result in a decrease in work supervision of its employees. Employees who feel that their rights cannot be fulfilled by the company will have implications for decreasing employee motivation. (Wahyudi, W. 2022). Maslow (Wang, R. et al. 2021) explains that a person's needs are met hierarchically. Someone tries to fulfill basic (physiological) needs, safety needs, esteem and social needs, and self-actualization needs. In fulfilling these needs a person experiences anxiety. To meet the needs of life, an employee wants to be able to improve his career so that income and self-image are higher so that his needs can be met. According to Rosyid (2003), an employee besides having to fulfill his life needs also in carrying out his duties and responsibilities at work is also accompanied by obstacles and challenges. Obstacles and work challenges are a form of stressor that allows perceptions of anxiety to arise regarding the issue of termination of employment and has an impact on decreasing work motivation. Obstacles faced by employees relate to certainty of work status and a sense of security from the issue of termination of employment. The issue of termination of employment greatly affects the psychological condition of employees so that it has implications for employee motivation. Employees who have high motivation at work can bring up high work performance and in accordance with company goals will not be affected by the conditions of the company where they work, while employees who work with low work motivation will harm themselves and hinder the achievement of company goals (Iis, E. Y. et al. 2022). Another research regarding the anxiety of the issue of termination of employment is Sholiha's research, Maratus (2017) entitled anxiety about the issue of the threat of termination of employment with work motivation. In this study, the anxiety experienced by employees due to the issue of the threat of termination of employment due to the condition of the company continuously losing money has an impact on employee motivation. With the issue of the threat of termination of employment, it is feared that employees who hear it will feel threatened both in terms of their work as well as in terms of the welfare of their families. A worker will experience disturbances in the cognitive, motor, somatic and psychological aspects due to worries about something unpleasant that an employee feels in a company. It is feared that this anxiety will also affect the work motivation of its employees so that it will have an impact on the company. Anxiety is tension, insecurity, and worry that arises because it is felt that something unpleasant will happen. Individuals experience anxiety because of their inability to overcome the problems they face. The worry increases when the problems are experienced piled up accompanied by fear of something that will harm them. If this anxiety continues, it will be difficult for employees to carry out their daily activities if they are not handled either by themselves or with the help of others. (Serrano-Fernandez, M. J. Et al. 2021). In the context of this research, it is the anxiety experienced by employees because of the issue of the threat of termination of employment due to the company's continuous loss

Empirical Research on the Issues of Termination of Employee Relationships Post Pandemi Covid-19. Urgency of the Role of Work Motivation and Employee Trust: Evidence from Indonesia

which has an impact on employee motivation. Anxiety is a feeling of worry, fear that is not clear why, but anxiety is also a great force in driving behavior, both deviant and disturbed (Gunarsa, 2009). From the discussion above, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: Work Motivation has a negative and significant effect on Termination Anxiety Issues Relationship between Employee Trust and Anxiety Issues of Termination of Employment

Lack of self-confidence can cause individuals to have feelings of worry, shame, panic, and other negative things which are influenced by a person's perception of himself (Gottlieb, M. Et al. 2022). Individuals who have self-confidence will not feel anxious about various things that will happen in their life. So that termination of employment that will occur at any time will not cause problems for both workers and the company. Individuals will be aware of the end of the work relationship so that each has tried to prepare themselves to face this reality (Postel-Vinay, S. et al. 2019). According to Ma'rifatullah (2017) the higher the self-confidence, the lower the level of anxiety. From the discussion above, we propose the following hypothesis:

H2: Employee Trust has a negative and significant effect on the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment.

III. METHODOLOGY

Measurement

The variables in this study were measured using a Likert scale with a range of 1 to 5 where 1 equals "Strongly Disagree" and 5 equals "Strongly Agree". The variables studied consisted of independent variables and dependent variables. Independent Variables include Work Motivation and Employee Trust. Work Motivation adopted from Hasibuan (2005) and Employee Trust adopted from 25, while the dependent variable is the Issue of Anxiety on Termination of Employment adopted from Ma'rifatullah, (2016). This study uses Multiple Linear Regression with the SPSS tool.

Sample

The sample in this study is the employee at PT. Marinal Indo Prima as much as 90 employees, the sampling technique is purposive sampling technique. That is by giving a questionnaire to employee at PT. Marinal Indo Prima. This research includes Explanatory Research..

Research Framework

Picture 1 Research Framework

IV. RESULT

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis.

The data processing uses multiple linear regression analysis which aims to measure the strength of the relationship between two or more variables. The variables used in this study are Work Motivation (X1), Employee Trust (X2) as independent variables that influence the Issue of Anxiety on Termination of Employment (Y) as the dependent variable. Based on the results of data processing using SPSS, the results are as in table 1 below:

Table 1. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	Regression Coefficient	t-test	Sig.	Description
Constant	74.932			
Work Motivation (X1)	-0,562	-5,762	0,000	Significant
Employee Trust (X2)	-0,351	-3,751	0,000	Significant

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Based on the multiple regression equation above, it can be seen that the conclusions are as follows:

1. The constant value is 74,932, which means that if the variables of Work Motivation and Employee Trust together do not change or equal to zero, then the variable Anxiety Issues of Termination of Employment is 74,932 which is not influenced by any variable.

Empirical Research on the Issues of Termination of Employee Relationships Post Pandemi Covid-19. Urgency of the Role of Work Motivation and Employee Trust: Evidence from Indonesia

2. The regression coefficient value of the work motivation variable is -0,562, which means that the Work Motivation variable (X1) has a negative effect on the Issue of Anxiety over Termination of Employment (Y). This means that if work motivation increases, the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment will decrease.

3. The regression coefficient value of Employee Trust is -0,351, which means Employee Trust (X2) has a negative effect on the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment (Y). This means that if employees have a high level of self-confidence, the lower the Anxiety Issue of Termination of Employment will also be.

Coefficient of Determination (R) The coefficient of determination is a value that indicates the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0,892	0,752	0,721	1.842

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Table 2 shows an R Square value of 0.620, which means that the Issue of Anxiety over Termination of Employment is determined by the variables Work Motivation and Employee Trust of 62%, while the remaining 38% is influenced by other factors not included in the independent variables of this study. This means that the selection of the variables of Work Motivation and Employee Trust is correct in predicting the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment.

Hypothesis test

T Test (Partial Test)

The t test is used to test the independent variables individually affecting the dependent variable. The t-test results for coefficients 1 and 2 can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of Partial Test Results

Variable	Regression Coefficient	t-test	Sig.	Description
Constant	74.932			
Work Motivation (X1)	-0,562	-5,762	0,000	Significant
Employee Trust (X2)	-0,351	-3,751	0,000	Significant

Source: Processed Data (2023)

1. The variable Work Motivation (X1) has a t count of -4.253 > t table of 1.67303 with a significance value of 0.001 less than 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05), and the regression coefficient is negative, so the first hypothesis states that " Work Motivation has a negative effect on the Issue of Anxiety of Termination of Employment " accepted.

2. Employee Trust Variable (X2) has a t value of -3.152 > t table of 1.67303 with a significance value of 0.003 less than 0.05 (0.002 < 0.05), and the regression coefficient is negative, so the second hypothesis states that "Employee Confidence has a Negative Effect on Termination Anxiety Issues" was accepted.

F Test (Simultaneous Testing)

The F test is used to test whether work motivation and employee self-confidence affect termination anxiety simultaneously by comparing the value of F-test with Ftable with the test criteria if F-test > Ftable then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. Calculation of the F test can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. F Significance Test Results

Variable	F-test	F-Table	Sig.	Description
Work Motivation (X1) and Employee Trust (X2)	56.962	3,10	0,000	Significant

Source: Processed Data (2023)

From Table 4 it is known that the results of the F test between Work Motivation and Employee Trust simultaneously have a significant effect on the Issue of Anxiety over Termination of Employment with a critical value in the F distribution at a significant level of 95% (alpha = 5%). So degrees of freedom/df = (n-k-1) = 90-2-1 = 86, then Ftable 3.10 and F-test 56,962 with a significance level of 0.000. Thus it can be said that the third hypothesis is accepted which states that "Work Motivation and Employee Trust simultaneously influence the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment".

V. DISCUSSION

Work Motivation has a negative and significant effect on Termination Anxiety Issues (H1 Accepted).

The results of this study prove that the hypothesis that has been developed is that Work Motivation influences Termination Anxiety Issues. The contribution of the influence of both is negative, meaning that the higher the employee's work motivation, the lower the level of anxiety about termination of employment, and vice versa. The results of this study also show that the statement that gets the highest score for the Work Motivation variable is that employees are motivated to work, because they have an obligation to meet clothing and food needs. According to Maslow's theory, each individual has needs that are arranged hierarchically based on levels ranging from basic needs to the highest needs (Hasibuan)³². The company's current condition is not good due to the pandemic, making employees feel in a state of uncertainty. Employees have high anxiety about the company's uncertain situation so that it has an impact on employee motivation. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Aisyah³³ and Widyantari³⁴ which stated that work motivation affects the level of anxiety about termination of employment.

Employee Trust has a negative and significant effect on the Issue of Anxiety on Termination of Employment (H2 Accepted).

The results of this study prove that the Employee Trust variable influences the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment. The effect of both is negative, meaning that the higher the employee's self-confidence, the lower the level of Anxiety Issues of Termination of Employment. There are many factors that influence Termination Anxiety Issues, as according to Goleman³⁵, which states that anxiety can be influenced by the level of self-confidence. Someone who has a high level of self-confidence will have better self-efficacy so that the individual does not feel threatened and safe. Employees who are confident so that they feel capable of carrying out their duties properly so that they are not haunted by anxiety or fear of the issue of termination of employment. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Ma'rifattullah³⁶ which states that the level of employee trust influences the issue of anxiety about termination of employment. Employees who have a low level of self-confidence will hinder their potential so that they always think pessimistically, are hesitant in making decisions and like to compare themselves with others. The results of this study prove that the variables Work Motivation and Employee Trust influence the Issue of Termination Anxiety simultaneously as indicated by the F test. This shows that the high or low level of Termination Anxiety Issues in this study can be determined by Work Motivation and Employee Trust as a together. Employees with high work motivation and self-confidence have a high level of anxiety about the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Work Relations. Someone who is able to motivate himself well to welcome the world of work will definitely have self-confidence. With a high level of self-confidence, the level of anxiety in facing termination of employment tends to be low, because individuals can quickly realize their anxiety so that they can suppress or minimize the impact of the Issue of Anxiety on Termination of Employment. Aisyah³⁷ in her research stated that there was a significant influence between employment termination policies and work motivation. High work motivation will make employees enthusiastic at work and have high productivity as well. High motivation is also an indicator that employees believe in their ability to complete their duties and responsibilities, so that if an employee has high motivation and self-confidence, it will reduce the level of anxiety about the issue of termination of employment. Ma'rifatullah³⁸ in his research stated that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and self-confidence regarding the issue of termination of employment.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that has been carried out, it can be concluded that:

1. Work motivation influences the issue of anxiety about termination of employment.
This means that high work motivation will reduce the level of anxiety about termination of employment. this means the first hypothesis is accepted.
2. Employee Trust influences the Issue of Anxiety about Termination of Employment. The higher the level of trust in the Issue of Termination Anxiety. This means that the second hypothesis is accepted.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

The results of this study indicate that the level of employee anxiety regarding the issue of termination of employment is in the high category so that companies can provide motivation to employees. Motivation can be done by providing direction, instructions, and also work evaluation so that optimal performance results can be obtained. Companies can also provide bonuses or other strategies to increase employee motivation and confidence. This research can be used as reference material and add to studies related to work motivation, employee confidence, and anxiety over the issue of termination of employment. Future researchers are expected to be able to add research variables, because it is not only work motivation and employee self-confidence that affect the problem of termination anxiety so that they can support and complete this research.

Empirical Research on the Issues of Termination of Employee Relationships Post Pandemi Covid-19. Urgency of the Role of Work Motivation and Employee Trust: Evidence from Indonesia

REFERENCES

- 1) Acquah, A., Nsiah, T. K., Antie, E. N. A., & Otoo, B. (2021). Literature review on theories of motivation. *EPR International Journal of Economic and Business Review*, 9(5), 25-29.
- 2) An, S. H. (2019). Employee voluntary and involuntary turnover and organizational performance: Revisiting the hypothesis from classical public administration. *International Public Management Journal*, 22(3), 444-469.
- 3) Anderman, E. M. (2020). Achievement motivation theory: Balancing precision and utility. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101864.
- 4) Arif, S., Zainudin, H. K., & Hamid, A. (2019). Influence of Leadership, Organizational Culture, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction of Performance Principles of Senior High School in Medan City. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 2(4), 239-254.
- 5) Braganza, A., Chen, W., Canhoto, A., & Sap, S. (2021). Productive employment and decent work: The impact of AI adoption on psychological contracts, job engagement and employee trust. *Journal of business research*, 131, 485-494.
- 6) Duggan, J., Sherman, U., Carbery, R., & McDonnell, A. (2020). Algorithmic management and app-work in the gig economy: A research agenda for employment relations and HRM. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 30(1), 114-132.
- 7) Eyoun, K., Chen, H., Ayoun, B., & Khlifefat, A. (2020). The relationship between purpose of performance appraisal and psychological contract: Generational differences as a moderator. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 86, 102449.
- 8) Gottlieb, M., Chan, T. M., Zaver, F., & Ellaway, R. (2022). Confidence-competence alignment and the role of self-confidence in medical education: A conceptual review. *Medical Education*, 56(1), 37-47.
- 9) Iis, E. Y., Wahyuddin, W., Thoyib, A., Ilham, R. N., & Sinta, I. (2022). The Effect of Career Development And Work Environment On Employee Performance With Work Motivation As Intervening Variable At The Office Of Agriculture And Livestock In Aceh. *International Journal of Economic, Business, Accounting, Agriculture Management and Sharia Administration (IJEBAAS)*, 2(2), 227-236.
- 10) Islam, M. N., Furuoka, F., & Idris, A. (2021). Mapping the relationship between transformational leadership, trust in leadership and employee championing behavior during organizational change. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 26(2), 95-102.
- 11) Kantorová, V., Wheldon, M. C., Ueffing, P., & Dasgupta, A. N. (2020). Estimating progress towards meeting women's contraceptive needs in 185 countries: A Bayesian hierarchical modelling study. *PLoS medicine*, 17(2), e1003026.
- 12) Kim, J., & James, J. D. (2019). Sport and happiness: Understanding the relations among sport consumption activities, long- and short-term subjective well-being, and psychological need fulfillment. *Journal of Sport Management*, 33(2), 119-132.
- 13) Men, L. R., Yue, C. A., & Liu, Y. (2020). "Vision, passion, and care:" The impact of charismatic executive leadership communication on employee trust and support for organizational change. *Public Relations Review*, 46(3), 101927.
- 14) Oakley, M., Mohun Himmelweit, S., Leinster, P., & Casado, M. R. (2020). *Protection motivation theory: A proposed theoretical extension and moving beyond rationality—The case of flooding*. *Water*, 12(7), 1848.
- 15) Postel-Vinay, S., Herbschleb, K., Massard, C., Woodcock, V., Soria, J. C., Walter, A. O., ... & Middleton, M. (2019). First-in-human phase I study of the bromodomain and extraterminal motif inhibitor BAY 1238097: emerging pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic relationship and early termination due to unexpected toxicity. *European Journal of Cancer*, 109, 103-110.
- 16) Rahnev, D., Desender, K., Lee, A. L., Adler, W. T., Aguilar-Lleyda, D., Akdoğan, B., ... & Zylberberg, A. (2020). The confidence database. *Nature human behaviour*, 4(3), 317-325.
- 17) Schultz, T., Frey, N. C., Hantanasirisakul, K., Park, S., May, S. J., Shenoy, V. B., ... & Koch, N. (2019). Surface termination dependent work function and electronic properties of Ti3C2T x MXene. *Chemistry of Materials*, 31(17), 6590-6597.
- 18) Serrano-Fernandez, M. J., Boada-Grau, J., Boada-Cuerva, M., & Vigil-Colet, A. (2021). Work addiction as a predictor of anxiety and depression. *Work*, 68(3), 779-788.
- 19) Sugiarti, E. (2022). The Influence of Training, Work Environment and Career Development on Work Motivation That Has an Impact on Employee Performance at PT. Suryamas Elsindo Primatama In West Jakarta. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 6(1).
- 20) Tóth-Király, I., Bóthe, B., Orosz, G., & Rigó, A. (2020). On the importance of balanced need fulfillment: A person-centered perspective. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 21(6), 1923-1944.
- 21) Wahyudi, W. (2022). Five components of work motivation in the achievement of lecturer performance. *Scientific Journal of Reflection: Economic, Accounting, Management and Business*, 5(2), 466-473.
- 22) Wang, R., Yu, R., An, B., & Rabinovich, Z. (2021, January). I2hrl: Interactive influence-based hierarchical reinforcement learning. In *Proceedings of the Twenty-Ninth International Conference on International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence* (pp. 3131-3138).